

SiC-MATRIX COMPOSITES FOR THERMOSTRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS EFFECT OF THE ENVIRONMENT

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ABSTRACT

SiC/PyC/SiC and C/PyC/SiC composites (usually with a SiC-coating) have been prepared by chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) and submitted to ageing treatments at 600-1400°C in vacuum and oxidizing (or inert) atmospheres. The oxidation phenomena occurring in the bulk or at the level of the SiC-coating are depicted and modelled. The key phenomena are (i) the in-depth diffusion of oxygen via the residual porosity, the SiC-microcracks and the fiber-matrix debonding areas, (ii) the gasification of the carbon phases and (iii) the formation of silica scales. At low temperatures, an in-depth oxidation occurs whereas at high temperatures, the materials often exhibit a self-healing character related to the plugging of the pores and microcracks by silica. Oxidation lowers the failure strength particularly during ageing at low temperatures.

INTRODUCTION

SiC-matrix (i.e. C/SiC or SiC/SiC composites) are potential candidate materials for thermostructural applications in oxidizing atmospheres in various fields, such as thermal protection of space vehicles or components of gas turbines. With respect to monolithic SiC-ceramics, they exhibit a non-linear, non brittle mechanical behavior, at least when the bonding between the fiber and the matrix is not too strong. In order to achieve this requirement, a coating, referred to as the **interphase**, is usually deposited on the fiber surface, prior to the deposition of the SiC-matrix on the fiber. The interphase has two important roles, namely, it should : (i) transfer the load from the matrix to the fiber and (ii) act as a mechanical fuse, deflecting the matrix microcracks parallel to the fiber surface, preventing thus the fibers from an early failure by notch effect. The most commonly used interphase material is **pyrocarbon** (owing to its strong anisotropic microtexture and its compatibility with both the fibers and the SiC-matrix at high temperatures) [1].

SiC-matrix composites are fabricated from uni- or multi-directional preforms made of carbon or SiC-based fibers. The former have the advantage of exhibiting excellent mechanical properties at high temperatures and are available in large amounts and at relatively low price. Conversely, they are very sensitive to oxidation even at temperatures as low as $\approx 500^\circ\text{C}$. The most commonly used SiC-based fibers are the Nicalon^(*) Si-C-O fibers. They are more resistant to oxidation but they undergo a decomposition beyond $\approx 1100^\circ\text{C}$ [2]. As a result, only carbon

(*) NL202 from Nippon Carbon, Japan

fibers could be used up to now to reinforce SiC with a view to applications at temperatures ranging from 1200 to 1500°C.

SiC-matrix composites have been designed to withstand exposures in oxidizing atmospheres at high temperatures and under load. Under such conditions, two factors could limit the lifetime of the materials : (i) the stability of the fibers with respect to temperature and atmosphere and (ii) the reactivity of the pyrocarbon interphase with oxygen. Furthermore, SiC-matrix composites are known to undergo damaging phenomena under load, including matrix microcracking and fiber/matrix debonding. These phenomena favor the in-depth diffusion of oxygen towards the interphase and the fiber. For all these reasons, a **coating** consisting of a glass-former material (e.g. SiC) is usually deposited at the surface of the composite (often referred to as seal-coating).

The aim of the present contribution is (i) to depict from a fundamental point of view the interactions that may occur between SiC-matrix composites (i.e. 1D-SiC*/PyC/SiC and 2D-C(**)/PyC/SiC) and an oxidizing atmosphere and (ii) to show their effect on the mechanical behavior of the composites.

1- EXPERIMENTAL

The SiC-matrix composites have been prepared from fiber preforms (1D or 2D), according to the chemical vapor infiltration (CVI) process at $\approx 1000^\circ\text{C}$ and under a pressure of a few 1-10 kPa [3]. A pyrocarbon interphase ($0.1 < e < 1 \mu\text{m}$) was first infiltrated from a hydrocarbon precursor (consisting mainly of CH_4). The SiC-matrix was then infiltrated from a $\text{CH}_3\text{SiCl}_3/\text{H}_2$ mixture, up to a residual porosity of 10-15%. A dense SiC-coating (thickness up to $300 \mu\text{m}$) was deposited on the external surface of most of the samples. Finally, some of the C/PyC/SiC composites were submitted to a stabilization heat treatment at 1600°C under an inert atmosphere. The stability of the materials with respect to the temperature and the atmosphere, was studied through thermo-gravimetric analyses (TGA) performed under vacuum or a flow of various gases (i.e. argon, Ar-CO mixtures, pure oxygen or reconstituted air) at different temperatures and for different durations. The related microstructural change was characterized by transmission electron microscopy (TEM) on thin foils prepared according to conventional procedures. The mechanical behavior was studied under tensile loading at room temperature after ageing treatments performed under various conditions. The failure surfaces were observed by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and by Auger electron microscopy (AES), when necessary.

2- RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

2.1- 2D-Nicalon/PyC/SiC Under Vacuum Or Argon

Uncoated 2D-Nicalon /PyC/SiC composites with a $\approx 0.1 \mu\text{m}$ PyC-interphase, undergo a weight loss when aged beyond 1100°C either under vacuum or an atmosphere of argon (fig. 1a). At a given temperature, the relative weight loss $\Delta m/m_0$ increases linearly as a function of the square root of time, suggesting thus a diffusion-based rate-controlling mechanism. The weight loss results from : (i) the thermal decomposition of the SiC_xO_y amorphous phase present in the Si-C-O Nicalon fibers known to be effective beyond $\approx 1100^\circ\text{C}$, yielding an evolution of CO and SiO gaseous species and (ii) chemical reactions between free carbon (present in the fiber and in the interphase) and the fiber decomposition gaseous products (mainly SiO), which progressively consume the PyC interphase and weaken the fibers. As a result, a degradation of the mechanical behavior is observed (fig. 1b) caused by both a weakening of the reinforcement and a weakening of the fiber-matrix bonding (the fibers being no longer bonded to the SiC-matrix for severe enough ageing treatments). The effect of the environment on the material, in terms of weight loss, is much less pronounced (and can be even suppressed) when the samples have been coated with SiC or the ageing treatments are performed under an atmosphere containing a high enough partial pressure of CO. In both cases, the improved thermal behavior of the material is related to

(**) an ex-PAN carbon fiber from Toray

the stabilization by CO of the SiC_xO_y phase. In conclusion, Nicalon/PyC/SiC composites can be used up to about 1200°C in inert atmospheres when they have been coated with SiC. This protection remains effective as long as the coating does not undergo severe microcracking [4].

Fig. 1 : Effect of an inert environment (vacuum or argon) on uncoated 2D-Nicalon/PyC/SiC composites : (a) kinetics of weight loss, (b) stress-strain curves at 25°C after ageing.

2.2- Nicalon/PyC/SiC In Oxidizing Atmospheres

Additional phenomena, namely oxidation reactions, occur in Nicalon/PyC/SiC composites when they are aged in oxidizing atmospheres (e.g. air or pure oxygen). As schematically shown in fig. 2a, oxygen reacts with the PyC-interphase with an evolution of carbon oxides (CO or/and CO_2), the formation of an annular pore around each fiber and consequently a weight loss. Thus, oxygen has to diffuse along those pores to continue to react with the carbon. During this diffusion, it also reacts with the pore walls, i.e. the fiber and the matrix, yielding an evolution of carbon oxides, the formation of silica scales (passive oxidation regime of SiC) and thus a weight increase. The weight loss and weight increase regimes are clearly apparent on the TGA-curves (fig. 2b), the former being predominant at low temperatures and the latter at high temperatures after a long enough time [5, 6].

Fig. 2 : Oxidation of 1D-Nicalon/PyC/SiC composites : (a) basic phenomena (schematic) [5] (b) TGA-curves, flowing pure oxygen ($P = 100 \text{ kPa}$).

The mass transfer along the annular pore and the oxidation phenomena can be modelled rather simply for 1D-composites [6]. The model gives among others, the length of PyC-interphase, l_r , consumed vs time, the thickness profiles of the silica scales along the pore and the overall weight variation $\Delta m/m_0$. The calculated l_r and $\Delta m/m_0$ values have been observed to be in good agreement with the experimental data for unidirectional oxidation tests performed on 1D-Nicalon/PyC/SiC rectangular samples coated with SiC on four of their six faces. The model can also be used to simulate the effect of various parameters, e.g. the temperature and the interphase thickness, on the oxidation kinetics. For a given interphase thickness, the PyC-interphase is consumed in-depth at low temperatures (e.g. 900°C) whereas oxidation is limited to near the

surface at high temperatures (e.g. 1200°C) owing to the plugging of the pore entrance by the silica scales (fig. 3a). In a similar manner at a given temperature (e.g. 1200°C), the pore plugging occurs more easily for composites with thin PyC-interphase (0.1 μm) than for composites with thick interphase (0.5 μm). Finally and as expected from the above discussion, the residual mechanical properties of the composites measured at room temperature, after an ageing treatment at high temperatures, are better for the composites with a thin interphase (fig. 3b) [7].

Fig. 3 : Oxidation of 1D-Nicalon/PyC/SiC composites : (a) effect of temperature (simulation) (b) tensile stress-strain curves at 25°C after ageing in air, of uncoated specimens [7].

In conclusion, Nicalon/PyC/SiC composites behave as self-healing materials when exposed at high temperatures to an oxidizing atmosphere, owing to the formation of a protective layer of silica (the effect being more pronounced in composites with a thin interphase). Conversely, at low temperatures the kinetics of formation of the silica scales become very slow with respect to that of the oxidation of carbon. As a result, the interphase is consumed in depth, the fiber-matrix bonding is destroyed and the mechanical behavior is significantly degraded. The oxidation resistance can be improved by : (i) depositing a SiC-coating on the composite surface, as already mentioned, (ii) reducing the thickness of PyC in the interphase (e.g. by using $(\text{PyC-SiC})_n$ multilayered interphases) [8], or/and (iii) replacing pyrocarbon by another layered material less sensitive to oxidation such as hex-BN [9].

2.3- C/PyC/SiC In Oxidizing Atmospheres

In C/PyC/SiC composites, there are now two constituents highly sensitive to oxidation at low temperatures, i.e. the fiber and the interphase. The oxidation rate of the as-received carbon fiber is higher than that of pyrocarbon, but both rates become similar after the stabilization treatment at 1600°C. The C/PyC/SiC composites are usually coated with a glass-former material such as SiC to better protect the carbon phases against oxidation. Furthermore, they exhibit even in the as-processed state an array of microcracks in both the SiC-matrix and SiC-coating, as well as partial fiber-matrix debonding near the matrix microcracks. These microcracks result from a mismatch between the coefficients of thermal expansion of the carbon fiber and the SiC-matrix, which yields residual stresses as the materials is cooled from processing to ambient temperatures (inset in fig. 4). During an oxidation test, oxygen can diffuse in depth via the microcrack array more or less easily depending on the temperature (the microcrack opening depending itself on temperature) (fig. 4).

The oxidation kinetics can be analyzed on the basis of three temperature domains (fig. 5). Below 800°C, the diffusion of oxygen in the SiC microcracks (which are widely opened, fig. 4) is fast with respect to the oxidation rate of the carbon phases. The latter is thus rate-controlling and the sample oxidized homogeneously in-depth (fig. 6a). At 800-1100°C, the oxygen diffusion in the microcracks becomes rate-controlling. The oxidation rate remains almost constant as T is raised (fig. 5), the oxidation of the carbon phases being more severe near the sample surface than in the bulk (oxygen depletion effect). Finally, beyond 1100°C, a self-healing behavior related to the growth of silica scales in the microcracks progressively takes place, as already mentioned in section 2.2 (fig. 6b). The microcracks plugging is favored by increasing the temperature since : (i) the opening of the microcracks decreases (fig. 4) and (ii) the rate of formation of silica

increases. As a result, oxidation is limited to the microcrack wall of the SiC-coating and eventually to the carbon phases located near the microcrack tips. When temperature is high enough (e.g. 1400°C), the composite undergoes no weight loss any longer (fig. 5) [10].

Fig. 4 : SiC-microcracks in a 2D C/PyC/SiC stabilized composite. Fig. 5 : Oxidation of a C/PyC/SiC stabilized composite in flowing air (100 kPa) [10].

Fig. 6 : Oxidation of a C/PyC/SiC stabilized composite (schematic) at : (a) 600-800°C and (b) beyond 1100°C [10].

Mass transfer and oxidation phenomena have also been modelled, focusing here on the oxygen diffusion in the microcracks of the SiC-coating (fig. 7) [11]. The model gives : (i) the oxygen concentration profile along the microcracks and the residual oxygen flow at the bottom of the microcracks and (ii) the oxidation rate of the carbon phases. It can be used to calculate the weight change $\Delta m/m_0$ and to simulate the effect of various parameters. As an example, the simulations have shown that a better protection is achieved with thick SiC-coatings despite the fact that such coatings exhibit larger microcracks. In a similar manner, they have shown that the self-healing behavior would be no longer observed (even at 1500°C) when the composite is mechanically loaded at a stress of 200 MPa (the SiC-coating microcracks being too largely opened).

The oxidation phenomena occurring during ageing treatments in oxidizing atmospheres, have a strong effect on the mechanical behavior at room temperature [12]. For a weight loss in pure oxygen as low as 2%, the R.T. tensile failure strength decreases by 30% whatever the ageing temperature (fig. 8). For $\Delta m/m_0 = 6\%$, it is more severe after ageing performed at low temperatures, i.e. 700-900°C (oxidation of the carbon phases in the bulk) than for those conducted at high temperatures, e.g. 1200°C (oxidation limited to the external ply).

Fig. 7 : Basic phenomena occurring during oxidation of C/PyC/SiC composites [11].

Fig. 8 : Tensile curves at ambient for 2D-C/PyC/SiC stabilized composites aged in oxygen.

Furthermore, the failure strength decrease is less pronounced when reducing the oxygen partial pressure in the atmosphere (e.g. when pure oxygen is replaced by air). Finally, the effect of the 1600°C stabilization treatment on the residual failure strength is positive when the composite is exposed to the oxidizing atmosphere at high temperatures (e.g. 1400°C) but negative for an ageing treatment at low temperatures (e.g. 700°C) (fig. 9).

fig. 9 : Correlation between ageing weight loss and residual tensile strength (arrows) at room temperature for C/PyC/SiC composites.

3- CONCLUSION

From the data presented in section 2, the following conclusions can be drawn :

(i)- The applications of SiC/PyC/SiC composites even in inert atmospheres are limited by the metastability of the Si-C-O fibers (Nicalon) presently used. Better results are expected with oxygen free fibers (e.g. Hi-Nicalon).

(ii)- The behavior of SiC/PyC/SiC composites in oxidizing atmospheres is better at high temperatures owing to the self-healing effect related to the pore plugging by silica. It can be improved by using both a SiC-coating and thin PyC-interphases. Further improvements (e.g. hex-BN interphases) will have to be used if the material is thermally cycled under load.

(iii)- C/PyC/SiC composites are sensitive to oxidation by both the fiber and the interphase and are microcracked in the as-processed state. Thus, they have to be protected by a glass-former coating such as a SiC-coating which is unfortunately itself microcracked. Oxidation is a bulk phenomenon at low temperatures whereas it is limited to the SiC-coating and the first carbon fiber ply at high temperatures. The oxidation phenomena strongly decrease the residual failure strength even at low weight loss.

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